

Studies on the Constitution of Spergulagenin A- A New Sapogenin from *Mollugo Spergula*

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Spergulagenin A, a new sapogenin, has been isolated from *Mollugo spergula*. It is a trihydroxyketone having the molecular formula, $C_{30}H_{50}O_4$. It has been shown to be a rare saturated pentacyclic triterpene.

The plant *Mollugo spergula* (Fam. Ficoidaceae) is widely distributed in W. Bengal and is used as a green vegetable. It is bitter in taste and is used in indigenous system of medicine¹ as antiseptic and aperitive, administered for the suppression of lochia. Its juice is applied in skin diseases.

The present investigation on *M. spergula* was taken up with a view to isolating the bitter principle. A systematic solvent extraction successively with light petroleum, ether, and ethanol (95%) was carried out and only the last extract had a bitter taste. The ethanolic extract was found to contain some bitter glycosides, mainly saponins which were precipitated from the concentrated extract by ether. The crude glycosides, thus obtained, were hydrolysed with ethanolic hydrochloric acid and the aglycone mixture was extracted successively with ether and chloroform at the room temperature. The above ether extract was washed with alkali and then concentrated when a fine colorless crystalline material separated; m. p. 272-82°. This product on purification by chromatography over acid-washed alumina and subsequent crystallisation from chloroform-benzene mixture had m.p. 278-82° (decomp.), $[\alpha]_D^{32} -31.4^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). The homogeneity of this compound was checked by thin layer chromatography over silica gel². It developed pink $\rightarrow$ violet colour in the Burchard-Lieberman test. This compound appears to be a new triterpenoid sapogenin and has been named as Spergulagenin A². Its IR spectrum showed bands at 3500 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl group) and at 1700 cm^{-1} (probably six-membered ring ketone). Spergulagenin A formed a triacetate, $C_{36}H_{56}O_7$, m.p. 236-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{34} +57.7^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), on heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride on a steam bath. The IR spectrum of the above acetate showed bands at 1740 cm^{-1} (acetate), 1700 cm^{-1} (six-membered ring ketone), and at 1240 cm^{-1} (acetate) but no band for free hydroxyl group. Spergulagenin A also formed a tribenzoate, $C_{51}H_{52}O_7$, m.p. 319°, $[\alpha]_D^{32} +78.9^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). A weak absorption at $280\text{ m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon, 1.17$) in the UV spectrum of spergulagenin A showed the presence of a carbonyl group which was confirmed by the preparation of a triacetyl-mono-2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, $C_{42}H_{60}O_{10}N_4$, m.p. 268-70° (decomp.). The carbonyl function appeared to be a keto group and not an

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1. Chopra, Nayer, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, New Delhi, 1956, p. 168.

2. Chakrabarti and Barua, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 339.

aldehyde as spergulagenin A triacetate was recovered unchanged after treatment with Killiani's oxidation reagent.

Spergulagenin A and its triacetate did not develop any colour with tetranitromethane, nor could be hydrogenated in presence of Adams' catalyst under normal conditions; nor did they react with perbenzoic acid. Moreover, the triacetate did not react with perhydrol in acetic acid.

Analysis of the NMR spectrum* of spergulagenin A triacetate also indicated the absence of any unsaturation. The probability of the presence of a cyclopropane ring, which is not uncommon in triterpenes, was ruled out as the triacetate was recovered unchanged after treatment either with hydrochloric acid or hydrogen chloride in chloroform solution.

A completely saturated triterpene of the molecular formula $C_{30}H_{50}O_4$ containing three hydroxyl groups and a keto group must be pentacyclic in nature. Spergulagenin A did not react with periodic acid, thus showing the absence of α -glycol or α -ketol system. Pyrolysis of spergulagenin A with copper-bronze did not furnish any formaldehyde, thus eliminating the presence of any formaldehydogenic group^{3,4} ($-CHOH-\dot{C}-CH_2OH$). Spergulagenin A did not respond to Zimmermann's colour reaction. Hence the keto group is most probably not located at C-3 position⁵.

Spergulagenin A, when oxidised with CrO_3 -acetone- H_2SO_4 , afforded only a neutral product, $C_{30}H_{44}O_4$, m.p. $279-82^\circ$ (decomp.). It is colorless and shows a negative ferric reaction and hence it cannot be a true α -diketone or an enolisable α - or β -diketone. It showed a positive Zimmermann colour reaction for 3-keto group⁵, indicating thus the presence of one secondary hydroxyl group at C-3 position in spergulagenin A. The above ketone on reduction by modified Wolff-Kishner method under anhydrous condition⁶ furnished a colorless product, $C_{30}H_{50}$, m.p. $187-91^\circ$. No detailed study of the above hydrocarbon has yet been possible.

It may be mentioned here that, so far, only a few completely saturated pentacyclic triterpenes, besides the friedelane group of compounds, have been reported in the literature. Spergulagenin A is a new saturated pentacyclic triterpene. Further work on the constitution of the above saponin is in progress.

**EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of the Saponins.—Air-dried, powdered material (whole plant, 500 g.) was extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus successively with light petroleum, ether, and ethanol

*Through the courtesy of Dr. S. K. Roy, University of Nebraska, Nebraska.

3. Tsuda and Kitagawa, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 1604.

4. Barua and Chakrabarti, *Science & Culture*, 1964, 30, 332.

5. Barton and de Mayo, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 897.

6. Barton *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1954, 2056.

**All m.p.s are uncorrected and were recorded in bisulphate bath. Light petroleum refers to b.p. $60-80^\circ$. Brockmann's alumina (E. Merck) was used for chromatography and acid-washed alumina refers to Brockmann's alumina, deactivated with 5% or 10% acetic acid.

(95%). A greenish gummy residue obtained from both light petroleum and ether extracts was devoid of any bitter taste. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to a small volume and excess ether added when a dark brown gummy precipitate was obtained. The solvent was decanted and the gummy residue was repeatedly washed with ether. The ether-insoluble residue had a bitter taste and formed copious lather when shaken with water, a characteristic of saponins. The crude saponin was dissolved in ethanol (75%, 500 ml) and refluxed on a steam bath for 5 hr. with HCl (conc., 100 ml). The mixture was then poured into a large basin and the ethanol was removed on a steam bath, keeping the volume constant by addition of water. The precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The crude saponin, thus obtained, was extracted successively with ether and chloroform at the room temperature. The ether extract was washed with aqueous 0.5% NaOH solution. The alkaline layer on acidification formed a yellowish precipitate which was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The ether extract after removal of the acid fraction was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On concentrating the above ether solution, a colorless crystalline material separated. It was filtered and dried; m.p. 272-82° (0.75g.). Removal of the solvent from the mother liquor provided a dark brown gummy material containing crystals. The above crystalline product (m.p. 272-82°) was dissolved in chloroform (10 ml) and adsorbed on a column of acid-washed alumina (50 g.). Elution with benzene (100 ml) afforded a small amount of a colorless glassy mass. The column was further eluted with a mixture of benzene-chloroform (2:1) and thirty fractions (70 ml each) were collected. All the fractions provided a colorless crystalline material, m.p. 276-82° (decomp.). These fractions were mixed and the mixture was crystallised from benzene-chloroform, m.p. 278-82° (decomp.), $[\alpha]_D^{32} = -31.4^\circ$. (Found: C, 75.84, 75.78; H, 10.64, 10.31; M.W., 480. $C_{30}H_{50}O_4$ requires C, 75.95; H, 10.55%; M.W., 474).

Spergulagenin A Triacetate.—A solution of spergulagenin A (500 mg.) in dry pyridine (7 ml) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was heated on a steam bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water, and dried. The crude product was dissolved in benzene (5 ml) and adsorbed on a column of acid-washed alumina (20 g.). Elution with light petroleum-benzene (1:1, 1.5 litres) furnished a colorless glassy residue which was crystallised from aqueous methanol, m.p. 236-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{34} + 57.7^\circ$. (Found: C, 71.97; H, 9.2. $C_{36}H_{56}O_7$ requires C, 72.00; H, 9.33%).

Spergulagenin A Tribenzoate.—Spergulagenin A (500 mg.) was heated with pyridine (5 ml) and benzoyl chloride (5 ml) on a steam bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice when an oily material separated. This was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed successively with 1% HCl, water, 1% sodium bicarbonate solution, and water. The ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was distilled. The residue was dissolved in benzene (7 ml) and adsorbed on a column of acid-washed alumina (24 g.). Elution of the column with light petroleum-benzene (2:1, 1.2 litres) provided a colorless crystalline material, m.p. 312-15°. This on repeated crystallisations from benzene-light petroleum furnished a product having m.p. 319°, $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 78.9^\circ$. (Found: C, 77.30; H, 7.89. $C_{31}H_{62}O_7$ requires C, 77.86; H, 7.89%).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone of Spergulagenin A Triacetate.—The 2,4-DNP was prepared in the usual way in methanolic solution. The yellow product was crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol as needles, m.p. 268-70° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.29; H, 7.56; N, 7.05. $C_{42}H_{60}O_{11}N_4$ requires C, 64.61; H, 7.60; N, 7.17%).

Oxidation of Spergulagenin A Triacetate.—A solution of spergulagenin A triacetate (100 mg.) in acetone (20 ml) was treated dropwise at the room temperature with a solution of CrO_3 in H_2SO_4 (500 mg. of CrO_3 , 0.4 ml of H_2SO_4 , and 1.4 ml of water) with constant stirring till the brown colour persisted (20 min.). Excess chromic acid was destroyed by adding methanol. On working up in the usual way, a colorless product, m.p. $236-38^\circ$, was obtained which did not depress the m.p. of spergulagenin A triacetate.

Perhydrol-acetic Acid Oxidation of Spergulagenin A Triacetate.—A solution of spergulagenin A triacetate (100 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was treated dropwise with perhydrol (0.7 ml, 100 vol., E. Merck) with stirring. The mixture was heated over a steam bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice. On working up in the usual way, the unchanged spergulagenin A triacetate was recovered.

Treatment of Spergulagenin A Triacetate with Acid.—A solution of spergulagenin A triacetate (100 mg.) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed with HCl (conc., 5 ml) at 130° for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On working up the product in the usual way, only triacetate (m.p. $234-38^\circ$) could be obtained unchanged.

In another experiment, dry hydrogen chloride was passed through a solution of spergulagenin A triacetate (200 mg.) in dry chloroform (10 ml) for 4 hr. at the room temperature. On working up the product, only triacetate (m.p. $235-38^\circ$) could be recovered unchanged.

Periodic Acid Oxidation of Spergulagenin A.—A methanolic solution (12 ml) of spergulagenin A (100 mg.) was treated with an aqueous solution of periodic acid (100 mg. in 0.2 ml water) and left overnight at the room temperature. On working up the product, only unchanged spergulagenin A was obtained.

Pyrolysis of Spergulagenin A with Copper-bronze.—An intimate mixture of spergulagenin A (100 mg.) and finely powdered copper-bronze (300 mg.) was heated on a metal bath at $325-40^\circ$ for 1 hr. and a slow stream of nitrogen was passed through the reaction vessel to carry over the evolved gases which were passed into a saturated aqueous dimedone solution. No precipitate of formaldehyde-dimedone derivative could be obtained.

Oxidation of Spergulagenin A with CrO_3 -acetone- H_2SO_4 .—To a solution of spergulagenin A (200 mg.) in dry acetone (200 ml) was added slowly a solution of chromic acid (500 mg. CrO_3 , 0.4 ml. of conc. H_2SO_4 , and 1.4 ml of water) at the room temperature with constant stirring for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Excess chromic acid was destroyed by addition of methanol. The solvent was almost removed under vacuum and the crystalline material obtained after addition of water was filtered and washed with water. The product was taken up in chloroform and the chloroform layer was washed with aqueous 1% NaOH solution. The alkaline layer did not form any precipitate on acidification. The chloroform extract was then washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained on removal of the solvent was dissolved in benzene and filtered through a column of acid-washed alumina. Removal of the solvent furnished a colorless product which on crystallisation from benzene-light petroleum melted at $279-82^\circ$ (decomp.). It depressed the melting point of spergulagenin A when admixed. (Found: C, 76.77; H, 9.09. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 76.91; H, 9.40%).

Wolff-Kishner Reduction of the Oxidation Product of Spergulagenin A.—Sodium (200 mg.) in diethylene glycol (8 ml, redistilled) was heated to 180° (all temperatures measured

with thermometer in liquid) and completely anhydrous hydrazine, prepared by refluxing hydrazine hydrate (20 ml, 100%) over NaOH pellet (20g. for 3 hr), was distilled in until the mixture refluxed freely at 180°. The reaction was carried out in all-glass apparatus, carefully protected from atmospheric moisture. The solution was cooled, the ketone (200 mg.) was added quickly, and the solution was refluxed overnight. The temperature was then raised to 210° by distilling some of the hydrazine. The mixture was refluxed at this temperature for 9 hr. It was cooled to the room temperature and then poured into crushed ice, acidified, and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained on evaporation of the solvent was dissolved in light petroleum and was filtered through a column of Brockmann's alumina. Removal of the solvent provided a colorless glassy material which was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 187-91°. (Found: C, 87.83; H, 12.00 $C_{30}H_{30}$ requires C, 87.81; H, 12.19%).

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